

THE FUNCTIONS OF THE IMAGE OF BIRDS IN FICTION

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In world literary studies, scientific research is being conducted on the study of the creative works of figures who distinguished themselves with their artistic works, the re-analysis of their unique place in the history of the people and nation, the assessment of the forms of poetic thinking, the works of various genres created by them from an artistic and aesthetic point of view based on the requirements of the new era.

In oral stories and written monuments found in ancient Turkic and Eastern literature, the image of birds and animals appeared from the earliest times and played an important role in revealing a certain idea and content in the works.

In the old literary heritage, the image of birds was presented more as figurative (allegorical) images, but later in classical poetry it was reflected both symbolically and figuratively. Birds were also effectively used in the form of visual aids and artistic details to ensure the artistry of the works.

“Symbol is one of the ways of depiction, only conditionally, a word or phrase with a figurative meaning within the scope specified in the context. Symbol is the use of a word in classical literature not in its literal sense, but in another figurative sense”.

¹Birds, which are frequently encountered in written monuments, legends, epics, and literary works of many peoples, are mentioned in their role in revealing the content of their works.

In the mythology of the ancient Irano-Sogdian peoples, the **Semurgh** is depicted as a symbol of a magical, omnipotent bird and is equated with Ahura Mazda. It resembles a burctite, with a beak, large wings, a body, and feathers, which also reflect a magical bird. This image is mentioned in the sacred book of Zoroastrians "Avesta" in the names "Varagn," "Saena Irgga." In the fairy tales of most Eastern peoples, we can see variants of the image of Simurg, such as the Bird of Happiness, the Bird of State, and the Nightingale.

The **phoenix** is the first appearance of this image, which we find in Greek folk mythology. In Greek mythology, the "Phoenix" or "foynik" is a magical bird. It has a very long lifespan, an eagle-shaped appearance, a yellowish-red, and an

¹ Куронов Д, Мамажанов З, Шералиева М. Адабиётшунослик луғати. Тошкент, “Akademnashr”, 2010. Б - 244.

inflammatory color. According to the description, at the end of his life, he burns himself and his nest with various fragrant firewood, and from his ashes, fresh poppies appear. Similar concepts are found in the concepts of the peoples of ancient Assyria, Ethiopia, and Egypt.

The image that receives the most attention in Eastern literature is the **nightingale**, which is often depicted as a symbol of "in love." In lyrical works, the image of the nightingale, along with the symbol of the flower, is one of the images often used to describe the separation of lovers, longing, and the impact of each other's beauty. This method of creating tomorrow's image is still traditionally used in fiction.

The **parrot** is a symbol of sweetness in Eastern classical literature. In Alisher Navoi's epic poem "Lison ut-Tayr," the image of a parrot bird is used as an image that is passionate about unattainable dreams and hopes, thinking only of itself, and arrogant.

The **peacock** is more often used in the works of classical literature as a means of reflecting the beauty, behavior, and graceful actions of girls. In some works, he is also depicted as a symbol of those who highly value themselves and pay much attention to artificial beauty.

The **dove** is more commonly found in the mythology of the peoples of the world as a symbol of the human spirit, peace, and harmony.

The **eagle** is given, especially in the literature of Turkic peoples, in the image of brave heroes who can achieve their goals without turning back.

The oras of such birds, which are often found in fiction, have important figurative and symbolic meanings, embodying, first and foremost, the human spirit, its rapprochement with the other natural world and its striving for it.

In his works, "every artist pays great attention to the language of symbols, strives to have an imaginative attitude towards the conditions in which he lives, the reality he feels, and to think figuratively".²

In fiction, one can encounter various ways of creating an image. This process arose in all peoples on the basis of oral literature, and later began to be reflected in written literature in a somewhat improved form. It is observed that the evolution of the formation of the image of birds has also gone through its own path of formation over millennia.

² Абдуллаев О. Ўткир сўз қолмаса... Жаҳон адабиёти, 1997. №3, Б - 98-104.